

Cross-linguistic Patterns in the Argument Structure of Posture Verbs in English and Spanish

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1 Introduction

In this paper I investigate the differences in the encoding of Path and causation in English and Spanish posture verbs (1-4), that is, verbs which describe the spatial location and configuration of the human body (e.g., *sit, lie, stand*). Specifically, I argue that the variation attested between these two languages is due to cross-linguistic differences pertaining to Path and causation encoding.

According to Levin and Rappaport Hovav (1995), it is possible to identify four meanings for posture verbs: a causative sense, an assume position sense, a simple position sense, and a maintain position sense. The causative sense (1a, 2a) selects two arguments and describes a caused change of state brought about by an agent or causer on a theme. The assume position sense (1b, 1c, 2b) describes an event of change of posture and necessarily involves a single animate entity to bring about the event. The simple position sense (3, 4) describes a state of location of an entity. Finally, the maintain position sense (3) is identical in form to the simple position sense, but it additionally implies that there is a deliberate “effort” in maintaining the state (3). Here I concentrate on the causative and assume position senses, and briefly discuss the simple position sense.

English, a satellite-framed language, can encode Path information by means of a satellite (1c), while Spanish, a verb-framed language, encodes this information in the verb (2) (Talmy 2000). On the other hand, the encoding of causation is pertinent to the explanation of the properties of posture verbs as well, inasmuch as these languages represent two different poles of the typology of causation encoding, namely, English follows the labile strategy and Spanish uses the anticausative strategy (1, 2b).

- (1) a. I sat the child (*on the chair)
b. The child sat (*on the chair)
c. The child sat down (on the chair)
- (2) a. Yo senté al niño (en la silla) (Spanish)
I sat to-the child on the chair
b. El niño se sentó (en la silla)
the child CL. sat on the chair

These differences will help shed light on the aspectual properties of these verbs in English, which some linguists have controversially singled out as a special class of state (Dowty 1979, Maienborn 2005, Rothmayr 2009) (cf. 3-4).

- (3) a. John sits on the floor (for an hour)
b. John is sitting

* This paper was presented at the Arizona Linguistics Circle 12, Tucson, 2018, and WECOL, Fresno, 2018. I would like to thank the audiences for their comments and remarks. I would also like to thank Jaume Mateu for his comments on a previous version of this paper. I alone remain responsible for any errors or omissions.

- (4) a. *El niño sienta en el suelo (Spanish)
 the child sits on the floor
 ‘The child is sitting on the floor’
 b. El niño está sentado en el suelo
 the child is sat on the floor
 ‘The child is sitting on the floor’

This paper is organized as follows. In §2 I outline the theoretical framework within which the present proposal is articulated. In §3 and §4 I discuss the properties of posture verbs in English and Spanish. In §5 and §6 I briefly discuss the aspectual properties of these verbs and conclude.

2 The theoretical framework

I assume Ramchand’s (2008) syntactically represented event-structure decomposition framework (5), in which the VP is divided into several verbal projections, each of which contains relevant Type-A information, namely, the category labels *initP*, *procP*, and *resP*. In turn, these correspond to subeventive projections identifying the subevents of a macro-event, that is, a causative subevent, a process subevent, and a result-state subevent, respectively. Following Mateu (2002), Acedo-Matellan (2010), and Ramchand (2014), I surmise that the different Path encoding patterns are a consequence of a language’s choice of lexicalizing Path in verbs or satellites, which in Ramchand’s (2008) framework instantiate *resP*. In short, each lexical item contains a rigid set of category labels identifying subevent components and participants (Type-A information), along with lexical encyclopedic content (Type-B information) (Ramchand 2014).

3 Cross-linguistic variation in the encoding of causation

In this section I present the cross-linguistic variation pertaining to causation in English and Spanish and argue that it can help pinpoint the syntax and semantics of posture verbs. In particular, in the assume position sense Spanish posture verbs appear with a “reflexive” pronoun, which allegedly deletes or demotes the Initiator of the event as it is considered an instance of anticausativization. In opposition to this view, I contend that the pronoun has an expletive-like function as it fills the empty Spec,*initP* and is bound with the lower DP in Spec,*procP* and Spec,*resP*.

3.1 Causativity from a typological view According to Haspelmath (1993), languages vary in the way they mark the relation between inchoative and causative verb pairs that share the same meaning. An inchoative/causative verb pair is defined as follows:

- (6) “[A] pair of verbs which express the same basic situation (generally a change of state, more rarely a going on) and differ only in that the causative verb meaning includes an agent participant who causes the situation, whereas the inchoative verb meaning excludes a causing agent and presents the situation as occurring spontaneously.”

(Haspelmath 1993:90)

In the case of Romance languages such as Spanish, French, and Catalan, the relation holding between them

is directed, that is, they use an anticausativizing strategy to create the inchoative and causative verb pairs. This is the strategy used with posture verbs (7-9). The causative and assume position sense of posture verbs is mediated by the appearance of a “reflexive” pronoun in the assume position sense. Germanic languages such as Swedish and German follow the same strategy (10-11). By contrast, English uses the labile strategy (12), that is, the intransitive verb is used to build the causative sense, the assume position sense, and the simple position sense as well.

- (7) a. Yo senté al niño en la silla (Spanish)
I sat to-the child on the chair
b. El niño **se** sentó en la silla
the child CL. sat on the chair
- (8) a. El pare va assure el nen a la cadira¹ (Catalan)
the father past at-sat the child on the chair
b. El nen **es** va assure a la cadira
the child CL. past at-sat-down on the chair
- (9) a. J’assieds l’enfant sur une chaise pour le faire manger (French)
I at-sit the-child on a chair for him make eat
b. Je **m**’est assis dans le fouteil
I CL.is at-sat in the sofa
- (10) a. Peter satte babyn i stolen² (Swedish)
Peter sat baby-the in chair-the
b. Peter satte **sig** upp i sängen
Peter sat CL. down on chair-the
- (11) a. Der Vater setzte das Kind auf den Stuhl (German)
the father sat the child on the chair
b. Das Kind setzte **sich** auf dem Stuhl
the child sat-down CL. on the chair
- (12) a. I sat the child on the chair (English)
b. The child sat down on the chair

What sets apart English from the rest of languages is its labile nature, namely, the same verb root is used for both causative and anticausative structures. The rest of the languages in the sample follow the anticausative pattern creating their assume position sense by means of a “reflexive” pronoun. Thus, each language’s choice has a bearing on the Type-A information codified in verbs. The labile behavior of English can be accounted for following Ramchand’s (2008) causativization approach, which assumes the existence of a null *init* head merged on top of the structure to introduce an initiational subevent that brings about the process (13a). In order to causativize, *init* cannot be specified in the lexical entry of the verb. In contrast, the rest of the languages mentioned will already include an *init* head in their lexical entries, which is exemplified below using Spanish *sentar* ‘sit’ (13b).

- (13) a. [[sit]] = < sit, <proc>, $\lambda e \lambda e_{proc} [e=e_{proc} \wedge sit(e_{proc})]$ >
b. [[sentar]] = < sentar, <init, proc, resi>, $\lambda e \lambda e_{init} \lambda e_{proc} \lambda e_{res} [e=e_{init} \rightarrow [e_{proc} \rightarrow e_{res} \wedge sentar(e_{init}) \wedge sentar(e_{proc}) \wedge sentar(e_{res})]]$ >

The lexical entry for English *sit* (13a), exemplifying the labile strategy, denotes a process, whose only participant is the Undergoer of the event. By contrast, the lexical entry for Spanish (13b), and any other

¹ Examples provided by Jaume Mateu (p.c.).

² Examples obtained from Viberg (2013:141).

language using the anticausativizing strategy, specifies that this verb contains the category labels *init*, *proc*, and *res* in its argument structure. As a consequence, the subject is not only the Undergoer of the process subevent, but also the Initiator and Resultee in the assume position sense.

3.2 A plea for autocausative meaning The fact that these verbs use a “reflexive” pronoun in the assume position sense and the additional fact that the event denoted by these predicates expresses a caused change of state (see §5) brought about by an Initiator on a Resultee, whose references are identical, should not be considered conclusive evidence for a reflexive analysis. By the same token, I argue that these pronouns should not be considered an instance of anticausativization either. First, I will qualify the latter claim with the pair of examples in (14-15), which compares the differing behavior of true anticausatives in (14) and posture verbs in (15). While anticausatives are incompatible with an adverbial phrase indicating the purposeful involvement of the subject, posture verbs in both the causative and assume position sense legitimate this element, which clearly sets apart these constructions.

- (14) a. El cristal se rompió (*deliberadamente) (Spanish)
 the glass CL. broke deliberately
 ‘The glass broke’
 b. El niño rompió el cristal (deliberadamente)
 the child broke the glass deliberately
 ‘The child broke the glass’
- (15) a. La niña se sentó en la silla (deliberadamente)
 the child CL. sat on the chair deliberately
 ‘The child sat on the chair’
 b. La madre sentó a la niña en la silla (deliberadamente)
 the mother sat to the child on the chair deliberately
 ‘The mother sat the child on the chair’

Secondly, the idea that reflexivity might be relevant for this construction has arisen in the proposals of authors such as Wierzbicka (1976), Kemmer (1988), and Geniušienė (1987); however, there is compelling evidence against such an analysis. As shown below, constructions with posture verbs (16b) are not readily interpretable as reflexive (16a), that is, as an action performed by an entity on itself that allows clitic doubling by means of an anaphor.³

- (16) a. Los niños se lavaron a sí mismos (Spanish)
 the children CL. washed.3PL to themselves
 ‘The children washed themselves’
 b. *Ana se arrodilló a sí misma (en el suelo)
 Ana CL. at-knelt to herself on the floor
 ‘Ana knelt herself on the floor’

³ The potential difference between (canonical) reflexives and posture verbs, or what Geniušienė (1987) labelled *autocausative* reflexives, must lie in their having different argument structures. Specifically, I propose that reflexive constructions contain a low ApplP (see Pylkkänen (2008) for a typology of ApplPs). Following Cuervo (2003), this ApplP would instantiate a static possession transfer relation, in which the dative argument is understood to be the (inalienable or alienable) possessor of the object.

- (i) a. Pablo le besó la frente a Valeria (Spanish)
 Pablo CL.DAT kissed the forehead to Valeria.DAT
 ‘Pablo kissed Valeria on the forehead’
 b. Pablo le lava el auto a Valeria
 Pablo CL.DAT washes the car to Valeria.DAT
 ‘Pablo washed Valeria’s car’

(Cuervo 2003:77-78)

As an alternative to these proposals, I would like to argue that the pronoun *se* in the assume position sense in Spanish has the function of satisfying the selectional requirements of *initP* to project a specifier. I adopt Pujalte and Saab’s (2012) view on clitic insertion as a repair strategy occurring in the PF branch whenever a required external argument has not been merged in the syntax. Rather than deleting or demoting an argument, the clitic’s function is to prevent the derivation from crashing when sent to the interfaces. Following Pujalte and Saab (2012), if a transitive verb with a D feature lacks a specifier in the external argument position, it will lead to a crash in the PF branch, since the verb’s selectional requirements wouldn’t have been met. Thus, the clitic is inserted post-syntactically to meet the D feature requirement of the head. The clitic that appears in this construction has expletive-like characteristics, since it enters the derivation with unvalued phi features that are later valued against a full-fledged DP in the structure through a probe-goal relation. The lexical entry proposed for Spanish *sentar* ‘sit’ (13b) renders a syntactic structure consisting of an *initP*, *procP*, and *resP* in both the assume position sense and the causative sense, but they differ fundamentally in the element lodged in Spec,*initP*: in the causative sense (17), the element in Spec,*initP* is different from the element lodged in the specifier of *procP* and *resP*, whereas in the assume position sense (18) the element occupying the specifier of *initP* is the reflexive clitic *se*. Thus, in the causative sense, one DP realizes the role of Initiator and another DP takes on the roles of Undergoer and Resultee. In the assume position sense, a single DP realizes all three roles by means of the reflexive pronoun, whose reference is determined to be identical with the reference-bearing DP below in the argument structure.

- (17) a. Ana sentó al niño en la silla (Spanish)
 Ana sat to.the child on the chair
 ‘Ana sat the child on the chair’

- (18) a. Ana se sentó en la silla
 Ana CL. sat on the chair
 ‘Ana sat down on the chair’

4 Path expression in Romance and Germanic languages

Another important source of typological divergence is the encoding of Path information. The verb-framed nature of Spanish allows the encoding of Path information in the verb root, identified here with the result portion of the event (*resP*) (Ramchand 2014). Following Mateu (2002) and Acedo Matellán (2010), the acquisition of a property can be conceived of as a Path; therefore, in the lexical entry of posture verbs the result portion of the event, if available, can be identified with the property of being *seated*. By contrast, the satellite-framed nature of English allows the presence of an additional element to codify the Path information of the event. These particles, or satellites, will be argued to identify the result portion of the event using Ramchand's (2008) *Result Augmentation*.

4.1 *The verbal nature of resP in Spanish* To check whether Spanish codifies result information in the posture verb, a temporal complement can be attached to elicit a result state-related interpretation which allows the length of the result state to be measured, as shown below:

- (19) a. Elisa se sentó (en la silla) durante una hora (Spanish)
 Elisa CL. sat-down on the chair for an hour
 'Elisa sat down on the chair for an hour'
 b. Elisa se acostó (en el sofá) durante una hora
 Elisa CL. at-lay-down on the sofa for an hour
 'Elisa lay down on the sofa for an hour'

In addition to this interpretation, it is possible to obtain an eventuality-related interpretation which measures for how long the event was repeated, over and over again. The ambiguity can only happen if the temporal complement appears with verbs, or constructions, with a result state (Piñón 1999). Additionally, verb roots may contain specific Path information indicating whether the movement is directed towards the Ground or away from it (20-21) (cf. Stefanowitsch and Rohde 2004).

- (20) a. Se sentó {en/*de} la silla (Spanish)
 CL. sat-down on/from the chair
 b. Se acostó {en/*de} el sofá
 CL. at-lay-down on/ from the sofa
 c. Se puso {en/*de} el escalón
 CL. put on/ from the step
 d. Se escondió {en/*de} los matorrales
 CL. hid in/ of the bushes
 e. Se quedó {en/*de} la oficina
 CL. stayed in/ from the office
 f. Se acurrucó {en/*de} la cama
 CL. curled-up on/ from the bed
 g. Se arrodilló {en/*de} el suelo
 CL. at-knelt-down on/from the floor
- (21) a. Se levantó {*en/ de} la cama
 CL. got-up on/ from the bed
 b. Se quitó {*en/de} la entrada
 CL. moved-away in/from the entrance

To sum up, the Spanish posture verb consists of a conglomerate of subeventualities instantiating the causation, process, and result subevent. No additional element is needed or permitted to fill in these meaning components, since all three of them are lexicalized by the verb root (13b).

4.2 *Result Augmentation in English* Due to its satellite-framed nature, English can express the Path of motion by means of a satellite, that is, an element morphophonologically independent of the verb.

Posture verbs in English count with a satellite, *up* or *down*, to express the Path of motion in posture verbs:

- (22) a. sit down
 b. bend down
 c. lie down
 d. kneel down
 e. bow down
 f. get up
 g. stand up
 h. curl up

This element can be integrated in the verb composite by means of Ramchand’s *Result Augmentation* operation, which allows the combination of a pure process (posture) verb and a particle. The verb meaning is built compositionally by the addition of a small clause-like structure containing the particle, *up* or *down*, which can further identify the *res* head in the verbal ensemble, since it is lexically specified with a *res* feature and allows the presence of a subject. This is shown in the tree below (23), which also includes a null *init* head on top of the structure to introduce the causation subeventuality, as argued for in the previous section.⁴

- (23) a. The man sat down

In addition to introducing a result state, the *res* feature of particles can turn intransitive process posture verbs into a transitive verb complex inasmuch as the subject of *sit* would not only be the Initiator and Undergoer of the event but also the Resultee. This satellite-framed transitivity is also at play even if a transitive verb with similar lexical-conceptual information, or Type-B information, exists such as in the case of *lie* and *lay*. I assume that the lexical entries of these verbs differ in complexity, that is, while *lie* is an intransitive process verb, *lay* is a full-fledged transitive verb containing initiation, process, and result subeventualities.

- (24) a. [[*lie*]] = < *lie*, <proc>, λeλe_{proc}[e=e_{proc} ∧ *lie*(e_{proc})] >
 b. [[*lay*]] = < *lay*, <init,proc,res>, λeλe_{init}λe_{proc}λe_{res}[e=e_{init} → [e_{proc} → e_{res} ∧ *lay*(e_{init}) ∧ *lay*(e_{proc}) ∧ *lay*(e_{res})]] >

⁴ Following Ramchand (2008), since the particle can identify the *res* head in the structure, and the DP can remain in Spec,PP, the verb-particle order is possible for these verbs as well, giving rise to sequences such as those below:

- (i) a. The man sat himself down
 b. The man sat down himself

A search in *Google Books* gets several examples of these verbs in combination with the particle *down*:

(25) If I **lie myself down** in a snow-drift.

(26) I had to go and **lay myself down**. I felt like I was going to have nervous breakdown.

In the case of *lie*, *Result Augmentation* allows the combination of the verb and the particle to create a verbal complex with a result subevent, whereas *lay*, a transitive verb, already contains a *resP* in its lexical entry. Thus, if *lay* is used in combination with a satellite, some of its category features, that is, *resP*, will necessarily be *underassociated* (27) (Ramchand 2008) to allow the appearance of the satellite realizing the *res* phrase (28).

(27) *Underassociation*

If a lexical item contains an underassociated category feature,

(i) that feature must be independently identified within the phrase and linked to the underassociated feature, by Agree;

(ii) the two category features so linked must unify their lexical-encyclopedic content.

(Ramchand 2008:136, (61))

(28) a. I lay myself down

5 The internal aspect of posture verbs

To conclude, I review the internal aspect properties of English intransitive posture verbs and compare them to the transitive default forms of Spanish, which do not allow the expression of stative events. Posture verbs in English have been argued to constitute an aspectual class of their own (29), since traditional descriptions of states and activities seem unsuitable for them.

(29) a. John sits on the floor

b. John is sitting

Dowty (1979) noticed that English posture verbs behave unlike canonical states as they are acceptable with the progressive, which should only be possible with events, that is, activities, accomplishments, and (some) achievements. These non-dynamic verbs, since they do not involve change, bypass this restriction (30). In the same way, they are ungrammatical with the phrase “*what x did was...*” when the event has an inanimate entity as subject, thus behaving as proper states. Their problematic behavior grants them the label *interval states*.

(30) a. The socks are lying under the bed

b. Your glass is sitting near the edge of the table

- c. The long box is standing on end
 d. One corner of the piano is resting on the bottom step

(Dowty 1979:173, (62))

- (31) a. *What the socks did was lie under the bed
 b. *The glass is sitting near the edge, and the pitcher is doing so too
 c. *The box is standing on end, which I thought it might do
 d. *The piano did what the crate had done: rest on the bottom step

(Dowty 1979:173, (62'))

Similarly, Maienborn (2005) notices that German (intransitive) posture verbs and other verbs such as *wait*, *sleep*, or *shine* in German seem to instantiate a different type of state, denominated D(avidsonian)-state. These verbs are set apart due to their passing eventuality tests aimed at identifying events such as perception reports (32-35).

- (32) a. Ich sah Carol am Fenster stehen
 I saw Carol at.the window stand
 b. Ich sah Carol warten / schlafen
 I saw Carol wait / sleep
 c. Die spanischen Eroberer sahen überall Gold glänzen
 The Spanish conquerers saw everywhere gold gleam

D-states (German)

(Maienborn 2005:284, (10))

- (33) a. *Ich sah Carol müde sein
 I saw Carol tired be
 b. *Ich hörte das Radio laut sein
 I heard the radio loud be
 c. *Renate sah Eva auf der Treppe sein
 Renate saw Eva on the stairs be

copula+SLP

(Maienborn 2005:283, (7))

- (34) a. *Ich sah Carol blond sein
 I saw Carol blond be
 b. *Ich sah Carol intelligent sein
 I saw Carol intelligent be
 c. *Ich sah Carol Französin sein
 I saw Carol French be

copula+ILP

(Maienborn 2005:283-4, (8))

- (35) a. *Ich sah die Tomate 1 Kg wiegen
 I saw the tomatoes 1 Kg weigh
 b. *Ich hörte Carol die Antwort wissen
 I heard Carol the answer know
 c. *Ich sah meine Tante Romy Schneider ähneln
 I saw my aunt Romy Schneider resemble

states

(Maienborn 2005:284, (9))

Conversely, these verbs do not pass other eventuality tests such as being embedded in the phrase “what happened was...” (36-38). This surprising behavior leads Maienborn to conclude that D(avidsonian)-states are an aspectual class of their own, since they pattern with events in perception reports and, at the same time, pattern with states, that is, stative verbs and copula predicates, when they are embedded in the abovementioned phrase.

- (36) *Das geschah während ... / This happened while ...* *process verbs*

- a. Eva spielte Klavier
Eva played piano
- b. Die Wäsche flatterte in Wind
The clothes flapped in the wind
- c. Die Kereze flackerte
The candle flickered
- (Maienborn 2005:285, (11))
- (37) **Das geschah während ... / This happened while ...* *D-states*
- a. Eva stand am Fenster
Eva stood at the window
- b. Heidi schlief
Heidi slept
- c. Die Schuhe glänzten
The shoes gleamed
- d. Eva wartete auf den Bus
Eva waited for the bus
- (Maienborn 2005:285, (12))
- (38) **Das geschah während ... / This happened while ...* *states*
- a. Eva besaß ein Haus
Eva owned a house
- b. Eva kannte die Adresse
Eva knew the address
- c. Eva ähnelte ihrer Mutter
Eva resembled her mother
- d. Eva hasste Mozart-Arien
Eva hated Mozart arias
- (Maienborn 2005:286, (13))

While Dowty proposes to treat these predicates as a special class that is only true if predicated of an interval, Maienborn assumes that they are a special type of state that contains the Davidsonian event argument (Davidson 1967). One of the problems posed by Maienborn's proposal is that, while in English and German it can account for the particular properties of these predicates, in Spanish it would incorrectly predict that the equivalent stative construction with posture verbs (42b) would be Kimian states, that is, properties, which are not predicated of the Davidsonian event argument, but rather of a Kimian event argument, following Kim (1969), that is, an ontologically different type of entity, as Maienborn considers copula sentences as Kimian states, whether they use *ser* or *estar* 'be'.

I would like to put forward that it is not necessary to introduce additional types of events in our ontology such as D(avidsonian)-states or interval predicates to account for the properties of these verbs; but rather, their basic aspectual make-up, that is, their having a single process subevent (*procP*) and the labile nature of English can explain their properties. On the one hand, I hold that intransitive posture verbs are better characterized as non-dynamic atelic events. In Silvagni (2017), it is argued that events and states differ in regard to the existence of a spatio-temporal point, or stage, exclusively, in the former. States are merely properties over individuals, hence spatio-temporal notions are not relevant to them. In his view, dynamicity should be considered an epiphenomenon of events rather than their defining property. Events can only be said to be dynamic if there is a sequence of stages, or spatio-temporal points, as a result of an action fulfilled by an entity able to produce such an event. Therefore, dynamicity derives from the idea that an action is applied over a stage. The property of being acted on belongs to events rather than subjects, thus, an action is fulfilled by an actant, be it intentionally or unintentionally, as long as such entity meets the requirements to generate such an event. I will identify this property of verbs with Ramchand's (2008) *initP*, which is only applicable to events that can be caused. Tentatively, I will assume that events that include this node in their first-phase syntax tree will be interpreted as dynamic. Once dynamicity is no longer considered a defining property of events, two main classes of eventualities arise:

- (39) a. States: *love, know, be yellow, be intelligent, etc.*
 b. Events:
 i. Non-dynamic events: *sit, lie, be ill, be tired, hang, smell, etc.*
 ii. Dynamic events: *wait, sleep, run, write, work, build, paint, clean, eat, sing, iron, etc.*⁵

As a consequence of this reconception, a change in Ramchand's (2008) basic types of events (40) is necessary to accommodate the assumptions about what defines an event. Since Ramchand's definition of process includes the notion of dynamicity (40b), I will redefine the denotation of process as a subevent containing a spatio-temporal unit to which an initiation event may be attached if the event is the result of an action carried out by an entity able to fulfill such an event.

- (40) a. State (e): e is a state
 b. Process (e): e is an eventuality that contains internal change
 (Ramchand 2008:44, (6))

The reconception of the internal aspect of eventualities results in the following first-phase syntax configurations for posture verbs in English:

- (41) a. causative sense: *init, proc, res*
 b. assume position sense: *init, proc, res*
 c. simple position sense: *proc*
 d. maintain position sense: *init, proc*

Finally, note that Spanish *sentar* 'sit' cannot be used in the same configurations as English (cf. (29) and (42a)), since its lexical entry contains all three subevent components (*init, proc, res*) (13b). This explains why a stative sense of these verbs can only be created through the resultative construction with the copula *estar* 'be' (42b). I assume with Ramchand (2018) that the participle instantiates the *res* subevent of the verb allowing, thus, a stative interpretation.

- (42) a. *El niño sienta en el suelo (Spanish)
 the child sits on the floor
 'The child is sitting on the floor'
 b. El niño está sentado en el suelo
 the child is sat on the floor
 'The child is sitting on the floor'

6 Conclusion

The properties of posture verbs in English and Spanish have allowed me to identify the sources of the observed cross-linguistic variation and conclude that it stems from the powers and limits of the syntactic information languages encode in lexical items, making sense of how that information is unfolded in the syntactic derivation.

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⁵ The examples in this classification of eventualities are based on Silvagni (2017).

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